

Hardware Implementation of the Self Assessment Manikin

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Abstract: The Self Assessment Manikin (SAM) is a feedback device created for pen and paper feedback on printed survey sheets. With the new constraints and requirements typical of modern experiments, many researchers have adapted the SAM to various software implementations.

This paper examines these various software implementations and their impact on related experiments and presents two novel techniques for SAM feedback that were developed using a PDA and a custom built hardware device.

Key words: *Self Assessment Manikin, Affective Computing, Experimental Procedure.*

1. Introduction

The Self Assessment Manikin (SAM) introduced by Bradley et al. [1] is a graphical method to allow a person to report their emotional reaction to a wide variety of stimuli. The use of the SAM involves self-reporting of a feeling on three graphical scales. Fig 1 shows a typical SAM survey image. The first line is for valence, happy to sad and the next is for arousal, very excited to bored or sleepy. The final scale measures control, from “in awe” to empowered.

Fig 1: The Self Assessment Manikin (SAM)

The SAM was originally printed on survey sheets and used as a feedback mechanism for participants in various experiments [2], [3]. Later works [4] used software to collect data and conduct the experiment. Some reviews are not always positive [5] but the SAM has become a standard for this area of research and has crossed over into other fields such as advertising [6]

Experiments where the SAM is typically used include:

- Emotion recognition
- Product evaluation
- Physiological Pattern Recognition

There are several problems in using the SAM in many experimental setups. Typically, the SAM is used in experiments where the participant is presented with some stimulus and some reaction is recorded. When the participant rates the stimulus using the SAM, a comparison is made between the reaction and the emotional state described by the SAM. The goal is ultimately to find correlations between the reaction and the reported SAM state. This is generally referred to as “emotion recognition”.

A particularly difficult situation is encountered when the experiment is using physiological signals (such as heart rate) as the response being investigated.

In this situation any participant movement will distort many key signals being recorded during the experiment. As such, minimizing user movement while interacting with the SAM and during the rest of the experiment becomes a key point of consideration. Typical artifacts and noise caused by SAM usage are shown in Fig 2. The shaded region indicates the time during which the user was interacting with the SAM.

Fig 2: Noise in EKG Signal produced while using a pen and paper SAM.

[Shaded region indicates SAM was in use].

For the purposes of this research, several criteria were defined to represent the needs of researchers using SAM feedback.

1. The SAM should be simple to use and have minimal emotional impact on the user and present minimal distraction from the experiment;
2. User interaction events with the SAM should be recorded with approximately 10ms accuracy;
3. SAM events must be synchronized with any physiological recordings made during the experiment (for purposes of artifact removal);

4. Allow the user to provide feedback and interact with the device in a manner that minimizes muscular action.

The last of these criteria is not straightforward to address. It is known that passive sensors recording electrical events in the body are easily overwhelmed by large muscle movement. Typical examples of such sensors include the electrocardiogram (ECG) and electroencephalography (EEG). Both these measurements are often used in experiments involving SAM feedback.

A ECG signal is typically detected below 1mV with information lying in the frequencies 1Hz to 70Hz. Electromyographic (EMG) output from muscle movement contains information between 7Hz to 20Hz with output as low as 50 μ V for small muscles and up to 30mV for the larger muscles. The presence of EMG noise is highly detrimental to the ECG signal [7] and the best solution is to keep the participant's larger muscles still. As the ECG is often recorded during experiments using a SAM and the signal is very prone to EMG artifacts, this paper will use ECG quality as a measure to determine if a SAM implementation can meet the 4th criterion.

2. Background

To introduce the current usage of the SAM we will cover three typical scenarios for user interaction:

- Printed answer sheets;
- PC Software;
- Integrated into the stimulus software.

A. Implementation of SAM as Printed Answer Sheets

The pencil and paper version of SAM [2] satisfies only the first of our four criteria. However it is potentially the best placed to address the first criterion. People are used to filling out surveys using pencil and it is thus considered to have a minimal emotional impact.

It should also be noted that this system is more reliable than its technological counterparts, however, it is possible that the data may suffer from human error during data entry when the answer sheets are tabulated.

Muscle movement of the user filling in a SAM answer sheet often involves the use of the forearm (activation of large muscles) and thus signal quality is degraded, as shown in Fig 2.

B. Implementation of SAM as PC Software

The SAM can be implemented in software and allow the user to provide feedback via a PC mouse/keyboard.

There exist several hardware arrangements to achieve criterion 2. Four have been used by various researchers:

- SAM on keyboard / mouse input;
 - via multiple monitor dual input computer;
 - via standalone application;
 - via a notebook [8].
- SAM on a touch screen[9].

A common solution to address the first three criteria is to use a computer to display the SAM and take participant feedback. There are many variations on this idea, but in essence, the user has a screen with a SAM displayed and a keyboard (and/or a mouse) to fill out the SAM with. This is shown graphically in Fig 3.

Fig 3: Generic PC controlled SAM experiment

One of the most logical, and widespread, technological adaptations of the SAM involves the use of a touch screen display. This is an extension of the dual input application but using a touch screen for user input rather than a mouse. This is a much more achievable goal than attempting to have a computer recognize two independent mice.

As touch screens are not a common experience there is a possibility that a user may be uncertain about using the device. However the simplicity of the interface can allow for the user to be less engaged with input tasks.

The touch screen does not address the 4th criterion as user movement is greatly increased during input. Specifically the entire forearm must move for the user to select an input option on the opposite edge of the screen, and traveling the arm up and down the screen requires bicep movement. This involves use of large muscles, and the result is a greatly degraded signal. Another drawback is that the user is brought into close contact with an LCD device that emits a broad range of RF interference, which may or may not affect the instrumentation.

C. SAM Integrated into the Stimulus Application

The most accessible software implementation for SAM based experiments to date is the Self-Assessment-Manikin Scales feature of the PXLab software [3]. This (open source) software offers several variations of the SAM and the ability to use the SAM to evaluate picture, audio and textual stimuli.

As with most standalone application implementations of the SAM, PXLab offers exact timing of all events. User feedback is accomplished with mouse and keyboard interaction.

EMG interference with this type of application can be minor as the user is only using the mouse and not changing arm position between the keyboard and the mouse. A typical sample of this kind of noise is shown in Fig 4.

However the participant will tend to keep one hand on the mouse instead of returning to a fully relaxed position, and hence a small amount of EMG interference can typically be observed during periods of the experiment where the signal would typically be cleaner under other SAM implementations.

Fig 4: Noise in EKG Signal produced while using PXLab.

[Shaded region indicates SAM was in use].

This constant background noise can be present while the user is receiving stimuli and to many researchers this is the most important time to have a clean signal. If constant evaluation of user signals is needed this may be a very good solution as the noise levels, though present, are reasonably low.

4. Method

A. Software Based SAM Utilizing a PDA

The software SAM apparatuses discussed so far do not present a strong solution to criteria 1 and 4. That is they may be a distraction for the user and do not optimize physiological signal quality.

We attempted a preliminary, but ultimately unsuccessful method to computerize the SAM in a manner that solves criteria 1 and 4. This involved the novel use of a PDA to present a SAM rating screen and receive user feedback via a stylus. See Fig 5.

Fig 5: Our SAM implementation on a PDA

The rationale for this method was to keep the natural feel of a pen and paper style interaction with minimized muscle movement. Muscle movement is greatly reduced because the fingers move to fill out the SAM and not the arm. If the participant is seated at a table and is free to place the PDA in a centralized position comfortable to them, then a survey can be completed with less major muscle movement than any other implementation investigated here. A typical sample of the signal produced while using a well positioned PDA for SAM feedback is shown in Fig 6. From Fig 6 a noticeably reduced noise level is present over the conventional PC readings shown in Fig 4

Fig 6 : Noise in EKG Signal produced while using SAM on a PDA.
 [Shaded region indicates SAM was in use].

The signal quality, however, is dependent on how well the participant has been coached to utilize the PDA and how easily the ergonomics of the environment allow the participant to go from a relaxed state to using the PDA. If the user is poorly coached then the result can easily be as bad as the other methods.

Fig 7 shows a (typical) example of noise levels in an experiment where the user was not coached or supervised. When this is compared to Fig 6, it is evident that a greater portion of the “in use” recording has resulted from noise.

Fig 7: Noise in EKG Signal produced while using SAM on a PDA (user is not coached). [Shaded region indicates SAM was in use].

Unfortunately two aspects of the generic PDA device made this kind of interaction unsuitable:

- Lack of resolution
- Real-time connectivity problems.

Resolution limitations of the PDA make some facial details of the pictures too difficult to recognize, see Fig 8 SAM character from: PDA (left), VGA (middle), paper (Right). Newer high-end PDA's with VGA resolutions come a long way to fixing this but still lack the detail to show SAM figures as rendered for pen and paper use [2].

Fig 8 SAM character from: PDA (left), VGA (middle), paper (Right).

To achieve criterion 3 the PDA software must communicate with the PC running the experiment. However it is technologically prohibitive for our PDA software to establish a useful connection with the experiment PC. The most flexible TCP connection available to many PDA's is the WiFi connection; however use of WiFi around ECG systems is not allowed in many countries. There is also an IrDA port that could be utilized but technologies for WinCE software to interface with this were not available at the time our experiments were conducted.

B. Hardware Based SAM Implementation

The PDA apparatus discussed here presents several deficiencies that made its use impractical. Additionally the need for user coaching was undesirable. With the goal of meeting all the experimental criteria, we built a hardware device to record SAM interaction. This device is shown in Fig 9.

Fig 9: Hardware SAM

1) User Interface:

The device utilized a white translucent panel with the SAM printed on it and a series of buttons under each picture to allow for user input. As the user presses a button, the device provides feedback by illuminating the picture selected with a diffuse blue light which filters through the translucent screen on the front panel to clearly highlight the selected choice in a non-distracting manner. Two additional buttons were provided on the device. These buttons can be given any label, but were for the purposes of this experiment given the labels “Next Slide” and “Stop”.

2) Technical Capabilities:

The device is accessed via a software API and can be utilized by the software running the experiment in real time. The unit is equipped with a piezo transducer capable of producing beeps of varying frequency, the volume of which can be set via a concealed volume knob accessible by insertion of a small screw driver.

A microphone is also present in the device and can be used to record the intensity of keystrokes (more vigorous key strokes produce a more audible clack inside the device). The microphone is intentionally not sensitive enough to make any vocal recordings so as to be amenable when obtaining ethics clearance for experimentation. The unit is further equipped with a relay capable of providing two levels of resistance to an isolated port on the device. This relay which can be controlled by the API is used to fingerprint recordings taken via by physiological recording devices so that data streams can be accurately synchronized with user activity during data analysis.

3) Signal quality:

The hardware version of the SAM showed a very clean “at rest” signal and produced an acceptable level of noise while in use. The “in use” noise is generally higher than the PDA solution shown here but is not so high as to make the system unusable.

Fig 10: Noise in EKG Signal produced while using SAM on a hardware device.

[Shaded region indicates SAM was in use].

Typical results for noise levels are shown in Fig 10. The noise is mainly due to a sliding motion of the forearm. A brief, sub heartbeat, distortion related to the action of pushing button is typically present. This is perhaps due to the device not being ergonomically refined, coupled with the small movement of the buttons on the device.

5. Conclusions

This paper shows a novel, hardware based implementation of the SAM. This implementation allows for user interaction with minimized impact on the physiological recordings generally obtained during experiments where the SAM is employed.

A selection of other SAM implementations were analyzed and a novel PDA based SAM apparatus was also developed and examined. Ultimately the hardware approach was found to be superior in situations where physiological signal quality is a concern.

Additionally it was possible for our Hardware SAM to provide many experimentally beneficial features such as data synchronization, interface pressure recording and interactive feedback. However the solution is not suitable for all applications. To assist people making a decision on SAM implementation, a summary of SAM suitability to different experimental considerations is shown in Table I.

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE FEATURE SMILE-O-GRAM OF SAM IMPLEMENTATIONS.

	Paper	PDA	Notebook	Dual input	Hardware
Usability	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Synchronized with data acquisition	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Detail of SAM pictures	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
User distraction	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
User muscle action	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Level of interaction	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Experimental flexibility	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Support for different SAM models	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊

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6. References and Citations

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